

ISSN No: 3433-7029

abstrajournals.com

892 Berne St SE, Atlanta, GA 30316, United States

Abstra International Journal of Economics and Finance

Volume 13 Issue 2, June 2024

117

NEXUS BETWEEN POPULATION GROWTH AND AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION: TESTING THE VALIDITY OF NEO-MALTHUSIAN HYPOTHESIS FOR NIGERIA

Samuel, Paabu Adda ^[1] and Agya, Atabani Adi ^[2]

^[1,2] Department of Economics, Faculty of Social Sciences, Federal University Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria

Abstract

The relationship between population growth and agricultural production has been a subject of intense debate and scrutiny, particularly in the context of developing countries. This study aims to investigate the intricate relationship between population growth and agricultural production in Nigeria, with a particular focus on testing the validity of the Neo-Malthusian hypothesis using Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) analysis. The findings of this study revealed evidence supporting the Neo-Malthusian hypothesis within the Nigerian economy. The findings indicate a statistically significant and negative relationship between population growth and agricultural production, suggesting that population growth exerts pressure on the agricultural sector. These have important implications for policy interventions and highlight the need for population management and increased funding for agricultural research and innovation which leads to the development of high-yielding crop varieties, drought-resistant plants, and sustainable farming practices that enhance productivity in Nigeria.

Keywords:

Population growth, Agricultural production, Neo-Malthusian hypothesis, Nigeria, Vector Error Correction Model (VECM), Time series analysis

INTRODUCTION

As the global population continues to grow, concerns about the sustainability of agricultural production to meet the rising demand for food have been intensified. Unchecked population expansion, according to the Neo-Malthusian hypothesis espoused by Thomas Malthus in the 18th century, would cause resource restrictions, which in turn would reduce agricultural output and exacerbate poverty. According to Magdoff and Tokar (2009), advocates of this theory argue that approximately 12% of the global population experiences food insecurity, hunger, and malnutrition, lacking reliable access to the necessary sustenance. The current rates of global food shortage can be attributed to several factors, including a decline in food production within less developed countries, a significant increase in population growth particularly in developing nations, rising food prices, and the expanding use of biofuel. Furthermore, the increasing prevalence of climate change and global warming, as well as the loss of crop diversity and the expansion of urban sprawl, significantly impact agricultural production. According to Kendall and Pimentel (1994), there has been a notable decline in per capita grain production on a global scale. This decline is

particularly evident in Africa, where grain output has experienced a loss of 12% since 1980. Moreover, Africa's grain production barely meets 80% of its consumption demands. The researchers concluded that if current levels of productivity are sustained, there would be a decline in per capita agricultural production by the year 2050. Furthermore, they assert that the potential for food insecurity to worsen is significant, surpassing even the most pessimistic projections. There is a divergence of opinions among scholars regarding the extent to which the Earth has attained its maximum sustainable population, sometimes referred to as its carrying capacity.

Nigeria, characterized by its expeditiously expanding population and substantial dependence on agriculture, presents an intriguing subject for examination to evaluate the applicability of this idea within the present-day framework. According to the [World Population Review \(2023\)](#), as of 2020, the population of Nigeria stands at 205,500,163 individuals. Projections made by the United Nations indicate that by the conclusion of the year 2050, the population is expected to increase to approximately 401.31 million. This data suggests that Nigeria is positioned among the nations experiencing rapid economic growth on a global scale. Conversely, it is observed that the growth rate of food production is only slightly higher than the rate of population growth, leading to an increase in the importation of food and a decrease in the overall level of national food self-sufficiency ([FOA, 2020](#)).

It is against this background that this study assesses the validity of the Neo-Malthusian Hypothesis in the context of Nigeria, where population growth and agriculture play critical roles in the country's development. The study intend to specifically investigate the following important objectives: examine the effect of a growing population on agricultural output in Nigeria, evaluate the effect of agricultural machineries on agricultural productivity in Nigeria, test the extent of relationship between population growth and agricultural production in Nigeria and provide appropriate policy recommendations capable of overcoming these challenges.

The paper is organized as follows: introduction, review of related literature, research methodology, results and summary of findings, and lastly, conclusion and policy recommendations.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The literature surrounding the nexus between population growth and agricultural production is diverse and multifaceted. This section will explore key theories, empirical studies, and debates that have shaped the understanding of this relationship. From the classic works of Malthus to modern interpretations of demographic transitions and agricultural innovation, the literature review will lay the foundation for a comprehensive analysis of the Nigerian case.

Empirical Review

The study conducted by [Bright \(2019\)](#) examined the relationship between population, food security, and economic growth in Nigeria. The researcher employed econometric approaches and analyzed time series data collected from 1981 to 2016. The study examined the correlation between government expenditure on social overheads and economic growth, finding a positive and statistically significant association. However, it also identified a negative relationship between food security, population, and economic growth. The observation of a notable rise in population growth has been linked to deterioration in both food security and economic growth, resulting in an increase in government spending on social overheads. It has been suggested that in order to effectively address the issue of population growth, policymakers should focus on various aspects including food production, food costs, social expenditures, impoverished populations, and fertility rates. In the study conducted by [Oduwole \(2009\)](#), an ordinary least squares regression analysis was employed to investigate the impact of population growth on agricultural productivity in Nigeria. The study's empirical findings indicate that agricultural output exhibits linear growth, but population demonstrates exponential growth. Specifically, population growth outpaces the rate of food production or output. [Aina, Falola, Amoussou, Oni, and Aribisala \(2019\)](#) investigated how the Nigerian population affected agricultural output during a 53-year period. To examine the pattern and trend of agricultural production, Ordinary Least Squares and Granger causality were employed to analyze the connection between agricultural

output and population expansion. Nigeria exhibits a population growth rate of 3.8%, positioning it among the nations characterized by rapid population expansion. On the other hand, food production rises marginally, at a pace slower than the population growth rate.

Oguntegbe, Okoruwa, Obi-Egbedi, and Olagunju (2018) conducted a study that investigated the relationship between population growth concerns and food security in Nigeria. The researchers utilized secondary data on food production index and population growth rate, collected from the years 1980 to 2011, to analyze the issue. The model was estimated using both Ordinary Least Squares regression and the Instrumental Variable approach. The results obtained from the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) analysis revealed an empirical relationship between population growth and food production, indicating a positive correlation. Nevertheless, the utilization of the Instrumental Variable Approach yielded a more intriguing finding: a notable decrease in food output is observed when the population growth rate increases.

In their study, Osabohien, Afolabi, and Godwin (2018) conducted an examination of the relationship between food security and agricultural credit facilities in Nigeria. The research utilized the Autoregressive Distribution Lag (ARDL) econometric methodology to analyze time series data obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin, Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), and the World Development Indicators (WDI) for the time span of 1990-2016. The findings obtained from the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) analysis indicate that there is a positive relationship between commercial banks' credits and the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund (ACGSF) and food security. Specifically, the empirical results reveal that a rise in commercial banks' credits is associated with an 8.12% improvement in food security. Similarly, the ACGSF has a positive impact on food security, albeit to a lesser extent, with a 0.002% gain. On the other hand, the analysis suggests that population has a negative effect on food security, as a 0.001% decrease in food security is observed with an increase in population. The research ultimately determined that population control can be achieved by the implementation of family planning measures, as well as the provision of sufficient funding for the Access to Contraceptives and Family Support Fund (ACFSF) by the government. Additionally, it is recommended that commercial banks be monitored to ensure that interest rates on loan facilities remain reasonable.

In their study, Jenkwe and Magaji (2016) utilized multiple regression analysis, employing the Statistical Package for Social Sciences, to investigate the impact of population growth on agricultural productivity in Nigeria between 2000 and 2016. Their findings indicated a positive correlation between agricultural output (AGOP), population (POP), commercial bank credits (CRE), and government expenditure on agriculture (GEA). The study has reached the conclusion that it is imperative for Nigeria to address the elements that contribute to population reduction and enhance the mechanisms for enhancing agricultural productivity.

The study conducted by Noor, Shri-Dewi, and Nor'Aznin (2015) employed the Vector Error Correction Method to investigate the determinants of food security in Malaysia. This study examined the many elements that influenced the food security model in Malaysia from 1982 to 2011. The evaluation of the influence of these elements is accomplished through the utilization of the Vector Error Correction Model method (VECM). The findings indicate the presence of a long-term causal relationship between the dependent variables and the explanatory variables.

The Theoretical Framework

Neo-Malthusian Model

This study relied on the theoretical framework of the Neo-Malthusian theory of population, which has proven to be a longstanding and relevant explanation for the challenges surrounding population growth and food availability.

The neo-Malthusian argument centers around a fundamentally rational concept that an increase in population, while maintaining a same level of per capita consumption, leads

to heightened strain on accessible land, food, energy, and various other environmental resources (Summit, 1992).

Malthus (1806) was the first scholar to broach the topic of food shortage as a pressing issue related to population dynamics. He posited that the global population will imminently surpass the planet's capacity to sustain it in terms of nourishment. According to Malthus (1806), the capacity of the population to exert influence surpasses the capacity of the earth to sustainably provide resources for human subsistence. Ehrlich and Ehrlich (2009) expanded upon Malthus' argument regarding population growth by positing that humanity would ultimately prove unsuccessful in its efforts to combat hunger. Contrary to their initial forecasts, the researchers saw noteworthy cultural patterns indicating that certain groups were indeed restraining their growth. Fertility rates in numerous affluent nations have declined to levels below replacement, while the Green Revolution has exerted a more substantial influence than initially anticipated. Nevertheless, the aggregate population experiencing insufficient access to food in 2005, which exceeded 850 million individuals, exhibited a level of similarity to the corresponding statistic documented in 1968 (Ehrlich & Ehrlich, 2009).

Quinn (1997) presented a counterargument to Malthus' scarcity hypothesis, positing that the increase in population is attributable to advancements in food accessibility. This hypothesis has been backed up by academics like Hopfenberg (2003) who used the dynamics of food production and agriculture to calculate the earth's carrying capacity. He calculated future population numbers based on past food production figures that were comparable to FAO estimates. The idea has received backing from scholars, including Hopfenberg (2003). The researcher estimated the Earth's carrying capacity through an examination of the interplay between food production and agriculture. The individual made projections for future population figures by employing historical data on food production, which exhibited similarities to the estimates provided by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO). According to Hopfenberg (2003), Malthus and Darwin were cognizant of the fact that populations have the potential to grow exponentially in the absence of limitations on resources, such as space and food. When resources become limited, the rate of population growth will decelerate after the population reaches the threshold at which the ecosystem's carrying capacity is fully utilized. The population is expected to decline until it achieves a state of equilibrium.

Although Hopfenberg (2003) and Quinn (1997) propose assumptions that are grounded in biology, their applicability to real-world scenarios, such as Africa, raises doubts about their accuracy and feasibility. This is evident in the case of Africa, where population growth has persisted despite a decline in food production, contrary to the predictions of the Malthusian model.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To examine the nexus between population growth and agricultural production, this study employs the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM). The Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) is a robust analytical framework that effectively reflects both short-run deviations from equilibrium and long-run interactions within a dynamic system. The dataset encompasses relevant variables such as agricultural production indicators, population growth rates, arable land, economic growth, and technological advancements.

If co-integration is confirmed, it can be inferred that APRO, POPG, ARL, AMAC, and GDPPC are potentially derived from error correction models with the following structure:

$$\sum_{l=1}^{\rho=5} \vartheta_l \Delta GPPC_{t-l} + \varphi_1 ECM_{1t-1} + \varepsilon_{1t} \quad \dots Eqt 3.5$$

$$\sum_{l=1}^{\rho=5} \vartheta_l \Delta GPPC_{t-l} + \varphi_1 ECM_{2t-1} + \varepsilon_{1t} \quad \dots Eqt 3.6$$

$$\sum_{l=1}^{\rho=5} \vartheta_l \Delta GDP_{PC_{t-l}} + \varphi_1 ECM_{3t-1} + \varepsilon_{1t}$$

....Eq 3.7

$$\sum_{l=1}^{\rho=5} \vartheta_l \Delta GDP_{PC_{t-l}} + \varphi_1 ECM_{4t-1} + \varepsilon_{1t}$$

....Eq 3.8

$$\sum_{l=1}^{\rho=5} \vartheta_l \Delta AP_{RO_{t-l}} + \varphi_1 ECM_{5t-1} + \varepsilon_{1t}$$

....Eq 3.9

Where:

- APRO = Agricultural Productivity (proxied by food production index)
- POPG = Population Growth
- ARL = Arable Land (hectares per person)
- AMAC = Agricultural Machineries/Tractors
- GDPPC = Gross Domestic Product (per capita)
- Δ = Difference operator
- α = Constant term
- φ = Speed or rate of adjustment
- ρ = optimal lag length

ECM_{1t-1} , ECM_{2t-1} , ECM_{3t-1} , ECM_{4t-1} and ECM_{5t-1} are the error correction terms respectively; while ε_{1t} , ε_{2t} , ε_{3t} , ε_{4t} , and ε_{5t} = error terms which are identically and independently normally distributed with mean zero and constant variance; β , γ , δ and ϑ are the error correction coefficients and are expected to capture the adjustment of ΔAP_{RO} , $\Delta POPG$, ΔARL , $\Delta AMAC$ and $\Delta GDPPC$ towards long run equilibrium, while $\Delta AP_{RO_{t-1}}$, $\Delta POPG_{t-1}$, ΔARL_{t-1} , $\Delta AMAC_{t-1}$ and $\Delta GDPPC_{t-1}$ are expected to capture the short run dynamics of the model.

RESULTS AND SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) Unit Roots Tests

The Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test is commonly used in academic research to assess the stationarity of time series data. Its purpose is to identify whether the variables being analyzed exhibit a unit root, which is crucial in order to avoid the occurrence of false results. The following unit root test displays the outcome of the stationarity test conducted on the series utilized in the model. The result of the ADF unit root test is as tabulated in Table 1.

Table 1: Augmented Dickey Fuller Unit Root Test at Level and 1st Difference

Variable	Level	1 st Difference ADF t-statistic	5% Critical Value	Prob. Value	Order of Integration
Δ(LnAPRO)	Non-Stationary	-4.453849	-2.954021	0.0012	I(1)
Δ(LnPOPG)	Non-Stationary	-3.586199	-3.580623	0.0494	I(1)
Δ(LnARL)	Non-Stationary	-4.661614	-2.945842	0.0006	I(1)
LnAMAC	Non-Stationary	-8.043903	-2.945842	0.0000	I(1)
LnGDPPC	Non-Stationary	-4.377320	-3.540328	0.0070	I(1)

Source: Author's Computation using E-views version 9.0

The findings presented in Table 1 indicate that none of the variables under investigation exhibited stationarity in their original forms. However, after applying the first

difference, all variables achieved stationarity. Stationarity is observed when the magnitude of the t-statistic exceeds the critical value at a significance level of 5%. This condition is observed in all of the time series that were analyzed.

Lag Selection Criteria

Before conducting the Johansen co-integration test, it is necessary to estimate the VAR lag length selection criterion in order to establish the appropriate amount of lags to be included in the model.

Table 2: Lag Selection Criteria

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	171.9505	NA	4.95e-11	-9.540031	-9.317838	-9.463330
1	510.6258	561.2333	8.27e-19	-27.46433	-26.13118	-27.00413
2	569.9937	81.41885	1.27e-19	-29.42821	-26.98410	-28.58450
3	663.3617	101.3709*	3.31e-21*	-33.33495*	-29.77987*	-32.10774*

Source: Author's Computation using E-views version 9.0

Table 2 presents the outcomes of the lag selection criterion. Before conducting tests for co-integration and calculating a vector error correction mechanism, it is crucial to ascertain the best lag length of the variables under study. The Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and the Schwarz Bayesian Criterion (SBC) are widely recognized methodologies for determining the optimal number of lags for variables. In this research, the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) was employed to determine the appropriate number of lags. As a result, a total of three lags were picked for the purposes of this study.

Johansen Co-integration Test

The Johansen test was conducted on the selected variables and the result is as tabulated in table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Johansen Co-integration Test Results

No. of co-integrating equations	Trace statistic	Critical Values		Max-Eigen statistic	Critical Values	
		Trace critical value (0.05)	P-value (%)		Max-eigen critical value (0.05)	P-value (%)
None *	150.4166	60.06141	0.0000	73.08444	30.43961	0.0001
At most 1*	77.33220	40.17493	0.0000	43.81283	24.15921	0.0000
At most 2*	33.51937	24.27596	0.0026	21.50539	17.79730	0.0132
Result:	Trace test indicates 3 co-integrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level			Max-eigen value test indicates 3 co-integrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level		

Source: Author's Computation using E-views version 9.0

The results of the Johansen co-integration test, as presented in Table 3.1, indicate the presence of co-integration among the series given in the model. The analysis reveals that the Trace test statistic and the Max-Eigen values demonstrate the presence of three co-integrating equations, each significant at a 5% level of significance. Based on the available information, it is justifiable to reject the null hypothesis (H0) that posits the absence of co-integrating vectors. Consequently, the alternative hypothesis, which suggests the existence of a long-run link among the series, can be accepted. Therefore, it can be established that there is a distinct long-term equilibrium relationship among the variables observed between the years 1981 and 2020.

From the Johansen co-integration output, a normalized equation of the long-run estimates ($LnAPRO = f(LnPOPG, LnARL, LnAMAC, LnGDPPC)$) is estimated below with a reversed table for the Long-run regression output.

Table 3.2: Co-integrating Coefficients (Normalized with standard error in parentheses)

LnAPRO	Lnpopg	LnARL	LnAMAC	LnGDPPC
1.000000	0.182981 (0.08228)	-0.530189 (0.07676)	-0.672620 (0.18245)	-0.183664 (0.02258)
t-statistic	2.223881	6.907100	3.686599	8.133923

Source: Author's Computation using E-views version 9.0

Table 3.3: Reversed Normalized Coefficients

Variable	Coefficient	Std Error	t-statistic	Sign. Level
Dependent	1.000000			
Explanatory				
LnPOPG	-0.182981	0.08228	2.223881	significant
LnARL	0.530189	0.07676	6.907100	significant
LnAMAC	0.672620	0.18245	3.686599	significant
LnGDPPC	0.183664	0.02258	8.133923	significant

Source: Authors' Reversed Computation from E-views version 9.0

In Table 3.3 Agricultural Production (LnAPRO) coefficient of 1.00000 suggests that, under zero or constant conditions for the other variables in the model, Nigeria's food productivity level is 1. As anticipated, there exists an inverse relationship between the coefficient of population and agricultural production. This aligns with the theoretical proposition that when a nation's population expands, there is a potential for agricultural production to fall short of meeting the people's needs, resulting in food scarcity. The presence of a negative correlation between the two aforementioned goal variables suggests that there is a deficiency in the amount of food being produced in Nigeria as a result of the escalating rate of population increase. This observation indicates that the demand for food, as determined by population size, exceeds the available supply of food, as determined by agricultural production. This observation is consistent with the findings of [Bright \(2019\)](#), [Oguntegebe et al \(2018\)](#), and [Oduwole \(2009\)](#), who have also reported a negative correlation between population growth and food production in the nation. The reasons put forth by Neo-Malthusians in [McDonald's \(1989\)](#) work, as mentioned in [Maisonet-Guzman's \(2011\)](#) study, provide additional validation for the claim that locations with larger populations exhibit a negative correlation with agricultural production.

On the other hand, the coefficients of arable land (measured in hectares per person), agricultural machinery (such as tractors and harvesters, serving as a proxy for technology), and income per person all exhibited positive and statistically significant relationships with the equation representing food production and population growth. However, it is important to note that despite these significant associations, there is no substantial evidence to suggest that these factors have led to significant improvements in food production that can adequately support the rapid population growth observed.

The findings suggest that while variables such as arable land, agricultural machineries, and gross domestic product per capita have the potential to contribute to food security in Nigeria, their impact is limited and insignificant in achieving food sufficiency due to the rapid and exponential growth in population figures over the years.

Vector Error Correction Mechanism

After conducting an analysis of the enduring impacts of the independent variables on the dependent variable inside the model, the study proceeds to estimate a vector error correction model (VECM). This estimation aims to ascertain the rate at which the series in the model converge, hence providing insights into the short-run dynamics.

Table 4: Extract of the Vector Error Correction Mechanism (VECM) Test

Error Correction	D(LnAPRO)	D(LnPOPG)	D(ARL)	D(LnAMAC)	D(LnGDPPC)
CoIntEq1	-0.173347 (0.15840)	-0.000244 (8.3E-05)	0.326323 (0.13683)	0.066250 (0.04615)	0.397802 (0.37444)
	[-1.09436]	[-2.92423]	[2.38486]	[1.43549]	[1.06238]

Source: Authors' Reversed Computation from E-views version 9.0

Based on the empirical findings presented in table 4, it is observed that the ECM coefficient pertaining to Agricultural Production (LnAPRO) exhibits the appropriate sign, namely -0.173347 . The findings indicate that an annual correction of around 17.3% is observed in addressing the disequilibrium or distortion within Nigeria's agricultural production. In order to achieve long-term equilibrium in the Agricultural Production equation, it is necessary for the Nigerian government to engage in a sustained five-year endeavor focused on policy development and implementation, population control, and enhancement of other variables outlined in the model. These efforts are crucial for attaining optimal yields in the agricultural sector of Nigeria. This implies that, under the assumption of other factors being constant, there will be a tendency for agricultural output and population growth to align towards an equilibrium trajectory during this timeframe.

Diagnostics

In order to validate the reliability of the model estimates for the agricultural production equation, the obtained findings underwent a series of econometric and/or parametric tests. The diagnostic estimates are presented in a summarized form in Table 5.

Table 5: Residual Diagnostic Tests

Type of Tests	P-Value
VEC Residual Serial Correlation LM Tests (at lags 3)	0.8976
VEC Residual Heteroskedasticity Tests:	0.3226
VEC Residual Normality Tests (Jarque-Bera)	0.0504****
Inverse Roots of Auto-Regressive characteristic Polynomial	Stable

***** All but one of the variables specified are normally distributed*

Source: Author's extract from E-views 9.0

The statistical data shown in Table 4.5 provides empirical evidence supporting the resilience of the relationship linking agricultural productivity and population growth. The model's estimations for economic analysis and forecasting were predominantly accurate. This is supported by the low probability values seen in the different measurements. The residuals of the model exhibited a predominantly normal distribution, with no major evidence of serial correlation, absence of heteroscedasticity, no severe threat of multicollinearity, and appropriate specification. The stability of the residuals of the models can be inferred from the inverse roots of the Auto-Regressive characteristic Polynomial depicted in figure 4.5. This is due to the fact that the residual values do not exceed the boundaries of the acceptable region. Based on the aforementioned evidence, it may be concluded that the residuals exhibit stability during the study period.

Figure 1

Inverse Roots of AR Characteristic Polynomial

CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The nexus between population growth and agricultural production is a multifaceted issue that demands nuanced analysis and well-informed policy interventions. Nigeria's experience, as illuminated by this study, demonstrates the potential for equilibrium to be achieved through technological innovation and strategic planning. By implementing

targeted policies that foster agricultural development and address resource constraints, Nigeria can navigate the challenges posed by population growth and ensure a sustainable and food-secured future.

Policy Recommendations

Based on the research findings, several policy recommendations can be made to address the challenges posed by population growth and its impact on agricultural production in Nigeria:

- a) **Investment in Agricultural Research:** Increased funding for agricultural research and innovation can lead to the development of high-yielding crop varieties, drought-resistant plants, and sustainable farming practices that enhance productivity.
- b) **Infrastructure Development:** Developing rural infrastructure, including roads, irrigation systems, and storage facilities, can reduce post-harvest losses and improve farmers' access to markets.
- c) **Access to Finance:** Providing farmers with access to credit and financial services can facilitate investment in modern farming equipment and technologies, leading to increased productivity.
- d) **Education and Extension Services:** Educating farmers about modern farming techniques through extension services can improve their knowledge and skills, enabling them to adopt efficient practices.
- e) **Population Management:** While promoting family planning is a sensitive issue, encouraging responsible family planning can contribute to a manageable rate of population growth, reducing the strain on agricultural resources.

Bibliography

- Aina, I. V., Falola, A., Amoussou, P. J., Oni, M. A. & Aribisala, T. (2019). The effect of population growth on the agricultural production in Nigeria (1961-2013). *Croatian Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 11(2), 230-236. <https://doi.org/10.17508/CJFST.2019.11.2.12>
- Bright, E.O. (2019). Population, Food Security and Economic Growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, 7(5).
- Dyson, T. (1994). *Population and Food: Global Trends and Future Prospects*. Routledge, UK.
- Ehrlich, A., & Ehrlich, P. (2009). The Population Bomb: Revisited. *The Electronic Journal of Sustainable Development* 1(3), 63-71.
- Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (2020). Nigeria Agriculture at a Glance. Retrieved August 18, 2023 from <https://www.fao.org/nigeria/fao-in-nigeria/nigeria-at-a-glance/en/>
- Hopfenberg, R. (2003). Human carrying capacity is determined by food availability. *Population and Environment*, 25(1), 109-117.
- Jenkwe, E. D. & Magaji, J. Y. (2016). The Effects of Population Growth on Agricultural Productivity in Nigeria between 2000-2016. *From the Selected Works of Confluence Journal of Environmental Studies (CJES)*, 10, 82-88.
- Kendall, H. & Pimentel, D. (1994). Constraints on the expansion of the global food supply. *Ambio*, 23(3), 198-205.
- Magdoff, F., & Tokar, B. (2009) Agriculture and Food in Crisis: An Overview. *Monthly Review*, 61(3), 1-16.

- Maisonet-Guzman, O.E. (2011). Food Security and Population Growth in the 21st Century. E-International Relations. Retrieved August 18, 2023 from <https://www.e-ir.info/2011/07/18/food-security-and-population-growth-in-the-21st-century/>
- Malthus T.R. (1798). *An essay on the principle of population*. Oxford World's Classics Reprint, Chapter V, 39-45.
- Malthus, T. R. (1806). *Essays on the Principles of Population*. Bensley Publishers, London.
- National Population Commission (2002). *Sentinel Survey of the National Population Programme: Baseline Report 2000*, Abuja, National Population Commission.
- Noor, T. A., Shri-Dewi, A. & Nor'Aznin, A. (2015). An Econometric Analysis of Food Security Determinants in Malaysia: A Vector Error Correction Model Approach (VECM). *Asian Social Science*, 11 (23), 1-11.
- Oduwole, O. O. (2009). Effects of Population Growth on the Agricultural Output in Nigeria (2000 - 2009). Retrieved August 18, 2023 from https://www.academia.edu/9148475/Effects_of_Population_Growth_On_Agricultural_output_in_Nigeria
- Oguntegbe, K. F., Okoruwa, V. O., Obi-Egbedi, O. & Olagunju, K. O. (2018). Population Growth Problems and Food Security in Nigeria. *Electronic Journal*. Electronic copy available at: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3330999>
- Osabohien, R., Afolabi, A. & Godwin, A (2018). An Econometric Analysis of Food Security and Agricultural Credit Facilities in Nigeria. *The Open Agriculture Journal*, 1(2), 227-239. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1874331501812010227>
- Pesaran, M. H., Shin, Y. & Smith, R. J. (2001). Bound Testing Approaches to the Analysis of level Relationships', *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 1(6), 289-326.
- Quinn, D. (1997). *The Story of B*. Bantam trade pbk. ed. New York.
- Summit, R. (1992). The "Earth Summit" on Population. United Nations Conference on Environment and Development: Population and Development Review, 18(3), 571-582. Published by Population Council.
- World Population Review (2023). *Nigeria Population 2023*. <https://worldpopulationreview.com/countries/nigeria-population>